

THE ISSUE OF RHYTHMS IN UZBEK CLASSICAL MUSIC

Nomonov Istiqbol Iqboljanovich

Andijan State University, Faculty of Pedagogy and Art Studies,
teacher of the department of musical education.

istiqbolomonov89@mail.ru

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ўзбек мумтоз мусиқаси. турли жанрлари, бадиий кучи, бетакрор жилваланишининг асослари.

Калим сўзлар: *мусиқа, санъат, анъана, жанр, лад, товушқатор, усуллар, услублар*

ANNOTATION

Uzbek classical music. the basics of different genres, artistic power, unique brilliance.

Keywords: *music, art, tradition, genre, mode, soundbar, methods, styles.*

Enter.

Method is one of the main links in the composition of music and is a factor that determines its order. In his book, “Uzbek Classical Music and its History”, Fitrat describes the method as follows: they mark the times between the niqras and the time between them (the time of the sound’s birth) and show the way to connect each other, such definitions have been found in the pamphlets of the research of almost all musicologists.

Literature analysis and methodology.

It is well known that Uzbek music is really based on two huge pillars and has been scientifically studied by musicologists, one of which is lad and the other is

method. In Arabic, "usul" (*singular "asl"*) means foundation. The meaning of this word corresponds exactly to the essence of the concept being expressed. In fact, the method, along with the lads, is the melody, the main foundation of music, one of the starting points of maqom thinking.

Results.

The topic of "method" has long been associated with the issue of "Iyqo". In the past, the treatises of musicologists have paid special attention to the issues of iyqa, which has been one of the main directions of research. Someone has been into the science of the rhythms of a particular pamphlet, while others have shed light on the methods, albeit partially, in their pamphlets. We can mention the possible scientific heritage of our great musicians such as Abu Abdullah Khorezmi, Abu Nasr Farobi, Ibn Sino, Safiuddin Urmavi, Mahmud Sherazi, Abdurahman Jami, Kamoliddin Binoi, Zaynulabiddin Husseini, Najmiddin Kavkabi, Darvesh Ali Changi, Abdurauf Fitrat.

To study the problem of methods in music and in particular the phrase "Iyqo" musicologist A. Nazarov gives a detailed explanation in his research. In his book, *On the Musical Rhythm of Pharoah and Ibn Sina*, in Arabic, the word 'iyqo' is a type IV verb derived from *vaqa'a* (falling, landing, splitting) and has general meanings such as "to compose, tune, mark". .

Discussion.

There is no exact historical information as to when Iyqo was formed as a special musical term, but the scientific definitions of Iyqo are given in almost all musical treatises created in the past. This, of course, indicates the great importance of the system of methods in music. Although the scholars' definitions of iyqa differ in content, they are essentially general and based on a single idea. In particular, the following are the most important in terms of content:

Farobi writes in his book *Kitabul Musiqi al-kabir*, "Iyqo is the movement along the naghmas (nukla) in limited quantities and proportions." In the treatise "*Kitabun fi-*

ixsa'il-iq'o", Farobi says describes "Iyqo is the transition to the azmina (nukla) of consistent equilibrium along the melodies of the radif (mutarodifa) sounds (savt)."

In his treatise *Murun az-Zahab*, Mas'udi gives a clear idea: "Iyqo means rhythm." One chapter of Abu Abdullah Khorezmi's *Mafatih al-Ulum* is devoted to the question of methods and gives a detailed explanation of all the complex methods of his time. And Iyqo is described as follows: "Iyqo is the movement along the tunes in limited quantities and proportions," an exact repetition of Farobi's (*Kitab al-Musiqi al-Kabir*) definition. Ibn Sina addresses the issue of iyqo in a number of his books. 'Ash-Shifa' and 'An-Najat' are among them. In these books, the following definitions of iyqo are given. "Iyqo is the measure of the time of refrain"; An-Najot. "Iyqo is a time composed of refrains, the first part of which extends between two refrains".

Safiuddin Urmavi also describes Iyqo in "Kitab al-Adwar" as "Iyqo - a limited number of azmina are the sum of the refrains between them (congregation)." Abdurahman Jami, in his treatise "Risoi ai musiqiy", states: "Limited azmina is the sum of the refrains of a regular advor." These definitions are described in detail in a study by musicologist A.Nazarov, who studied the science of iyqo.

Well-known status scientist I. Rajabov, on the other hand, summed up all the definitions in his book *Maqomlar* and gave the following definition to Iyqo: 1. musical sounds and the style of performance of musical works in general (this includes practice); 2. Rhythm measurement, system of rhythms in musical works and poems; a special science that studies such rhythm. "

Summary.

Regarding the fact that before the system of iyqa mentioned in the treatises of medieval scholars there was a system of specific methods in practice, A. Nazarov states in his research. He writes: - In the IX-X centuries in the "high style" of Arabic music practice in the broadest sense there is a classical rhythmic series, in which the rhythm of all types and genres of music of this period is reflected in the form of theoretical-empirical system.

ФОЙДАЛАНИЛГАН АДАБИЁТЛАР РЎЙХАТИ

1. Marufjon, R. (2022). A Matter of Rhythm in Oriental Classical Music. Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress, 1(6), 80-84.
2. Маъруфжон Мамиржон Ўғли Расулов, & С.М.Бегматов (2022). МАҚОМЛАРДА УСУЛЛАР ЎРНИ ВА АҲАМИЯТИ (ФАРҒОНА ТОШКЕНТ МАҚОМ ЙЎЛЛАРИ УСУЛЛАРИ МИСОЛИДА). Oriental Art and Culture, 3 (2), 810-821.
3. Marufjon, R., & Begmatov, S. M. (2023). Music by Uzbek Mumtaz Shashmaqom. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF ARTS AND DESIGN, 4(1), 33-36.
4. Акбаров И. Муסיқа луғати. Тшкент. 1997 й.
5. Абдуллаев Р. Ўзбек мумтоз муסיқаси Тошкент: 2008 й.
6. Виноградов В.С. Классические традиции Иранской музыки.
7. Гафурбеков Т. Фолклорные истоки узбекского профессионального творчества. Тошкент: “Ўқитувчи”, 1984 й.
8. Джами Абдурахман. Трактат о музыке. /Пер. С перс. А.Н.Болдырева. коммент. В.М.Беляева. Тошкент. 1960 й.
9. Жабборов А. Ўзбекистон бастакорлари ва муסיқашунослари. Тошкент: “Янги аср авлоди”, 2004 й.
10. Ибн Сино Абу Али. Жавомиъ ил мул-муסיкий. Қоҳира , 1956 г.
11. Маъруфжон Мамиржон Ўғли Расулов (2023). ШАШМАҚОМ УСУЛЛАРИ ҲАҚИДА. Oriental Art and Culture, 4 (2), 729-735.
12. Rasulov Marufjon Mamirjon Ogli (2023). WAYS OF MAQAM OF THE TECHNIQUE OF UFAR AND FORMS AND FEATURES IN THE COMPOSITION OF FOLK MUSIC. European Journal of Arts, (2), 20-29.

13. Маъруфжон Мамиржон Ўғли Расулов (2023). ЎЗБЕК МАҚОМОТИ УСУЛЛАР ТИЗИМИ: МУАЙЯН УСУЛ ВА ТУРКУМИЙЛИК КЕСИМИДА (ФАРҒОНА ТОШКЕНТ МАҚОМ ЙЎЛЛАРИ МИСОЛИДА). *Oriental Art and Culture*, 4 (4), 212-231.

14. Маъруфжон Мамиржон Ўғли Расулов (2023). ФАРҒОНА-ТОШКЕНТ МАҚОМ ЙЎЛЛАРИ ҲУСУСИДА. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 4 (3), 22-30.

15. https://ppublishing.org/media/uploads/journals/article/Arts-2_23_p20-29.pdf

16. https://scholar.google.ru/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=UZ7Sh6oAAAAJ&citation_for_view=UZ7Sh6oAAAAJ:Y0pCki6q_DkC